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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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The Way Life Works

I always wondered how life starts
Not in the grand or fancy parts,
But in the quiet things we miss,
Like leaves that curl, or cells that split.

It's strange to think inside our skin
A thousand things move, rush, begin.
Enzymes working, tissues growing
All of it, without us knowing.

And when I watch a bird take flight,
Or see roots search for soil and light,
I'm reminded life's not hard to see
It's in everything, including me.

Biology, in its own way,
Makes ordinary things feel brave.
It shows me life from small to tall
And somehow, it makes me love it all